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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of improving English language teaching methodology based on electronic educational resources. The role of the effective use of digital technologies, electronic textbooks, interactive platforms, mobile applications, and multimedia tools in the educational process in developing students' language competencies is highlighted. Additionally, modern pedagogical approaches and interactive methods serving the development of listening, reading, writing, and oral speech skills using electronic educational resources are analyzed. The article develops scientific and practical recommendations for improving the methodology of teaching English.

Keywords: electronic educational resources, English language teaching, interactive learning, multimedia technologies, online educational platforms, mobile learning, independent study, electronic textbooks.

Introduction

Today's globalization and digital transformation processes require new approaches at all levels of the education system. In particular, the use of modern information and communication technologies and electronic educational resources in teaching foreign languages, in particular English, is recognized as one of the important factors in improving the quality of education. This is because English is of particular importance not only as a means of international communication but also as a language of science, technology, business, the digital economy, and global information exchange. Therefore, effective English language teaching, the formation of students' communicative competence, and the development of listening, reading, writing, and oral speech skills are among the urgent tasks facing modern education.

While in the traditional educational process, teaching English was often limited to textbooks, dictionaries, grammatical exercises, and teacher explanations, in the current digital era, the needs, interests, and individual capabilities of the learner have fundamentally changed. The modern student is more inclined to quickly perceive information, learn through visual and audio materials, engage in independent research, and engage in interactive activities. In

such conditions, the methodology of teaching English must also transition from a static form to a dynamic, flexible, and innovative one. Electronic educational resources are emerging as an effective tool that can meet this need.

Electronic educational resources include electronic textbooks, multimedia materials, audio and video lessons, interactive exercises, online tests, virtual dictionaries, mobile applications, distance learning platforms, artificial intelligence-based curricula, and digital assessment tools. Such resources serve to organize the educational process in teaching English more interesting, effective and effective. For example, the use of audio texts, podcasts, and video lessons in developing listening comprehension skills enhances students' ability to understand real-world speech. In developing oral speech, interactive platforms, video communication tools, and chatbots create a practical communication environment for students. Electronic writing editors, automated verification systems, and online assignments play a crucial role in the formation of written speech.

Another important aspect of e-learning resources is that they allow for the individualization of the educational process. Each student learns English at a different pace, in a different style, and based on different needs. In a traditional lesson process, it is difficult for the teacher to fully address the individual needs of all students at once. Electronic resources allow students to work independently, re-perform assignments, see their own mistakes, select materials appropriate to their level of knowledge, and monitor the learning process. As a result, the student becomes not a passive participant in the educational process, but an active subject.

Furthermore, e-learning resources are an effective tool for increasing motivation in English language teaching. It is well known that a student's intrinsic interest, active participation, and regular practice are of great importance in learning a foreign language. Elements of gamification, rating systems, interactive tasks, visual materials, and real-life communicative situations used on digital platforms enhance students' interest in the lesson. Especially when learning English, it is important to apply grammatical rules in practical situations rather than memorizing the text or memorizing them mechanically. Electronic educational resources help create an environment oriented specifically toward this practical activity.

Today, the use of e-learning resources in the education system is becoming not only an additional tool but also an integral part of teaching methodology. However, this process is not effective on its own. To ensure the effectiveness of

using electronic resources, it is necessary to select them in accordance with the lesson goal, students' age, language proficiency level, topic content, and expected results. Otherwise, instead of improving the quality of education, digital tools can become a distracting factor for the student. Therefore, the issue of the methodologically correct use of electronic educational resources in teaching English is of particular scientific and practical importance.

Improving the methodology of teaching English based on electronic educational resources is primarily related to enriching educational content, interactivating the lesson process, developing students' independent learning skills, and modernizing the assessment process. At the same time, electronic resources should be viewed not as a simple technical tool, but as an element of a methodological system serving a didactic purpose. This is because any technology increases the effectiveness of education only when it is used purposefully, meaningfully, and methodically by the teacher.

Discussion

The issue of improving the methodology of teaching English based on electronic educational resources is of particular importance in today's educational process. This is because a modern student effectively learns in an educational environment focused on interactive, visual, audio, and practical activities rather than traditional forms of instruction. The English language is not just a set of grammatical rules, but a means of real communication, information exchange, and intercultural communication. Therefore, the use of e-learning resources in its teaching is not a simple technical innovation, but a methodological necessity.

First and foremost, e-learning resources allow for the enrichment of lesson content when teaching English. The text, exercises, and grammatical tasks provided in traditional textbooks are often limited in scope. Electronic resources allow the teacher to enrich the topic with audio, video, animation, interactive exercises, and real-life situations. For example, when teaching topics such as "Traveling," "Education," "Environment," and "Technology," the use of short videos, authentic dialogues, online articles, infographics, and virtual assignments increases students' interest in the topic. This approach brings the language learning process closer to natural communicative activity from artificial exercise.

One of the important aspects to be discussed is that e-learning resources serve the comprehensive development of four main speech activities in English: listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Audio materials, podcasts, subtitled videos, and interactive listening exercises yield effective

results in developing listening comprehension skills. The student is introduced to various pronunciations, intonations, speech speed, and real communicative situations. This prepares the student to perceive natural English, unlike the standard audio texts in the textbook.

The capabilities of electronic resources in developing speaking skills are even broader. Video communication platforms, recording software, AI-based chatbots, and interactive dialogues allow the student to practice independently. In a traditional classroom setting, it can be difficult to give all students adequate opportunities to speak. Electronic tools reduce this limitation. The student can record and listen to their speech, analyze their mistakes, improve their pronunciation, and actively participate in communication situations. This process creates a favorable psychological environment, especially for students with low self-confidence.

Electronic texts, online articles, digital libraries, and interactive dictionaries are of great importance in developing reading skills. In the process of working with electronic texts, the student can quickly determine the meaning of unfamiliar words, complete test tasks on the text, highlight the main idea, and independently analyze the content of the text. In this case, the reading process is not limited to translating the text, but becomes an activity of critical thinking, sorting information and understanding the content.

Electronic writing editors, automatic spelling and grammar checker programs, online forums, and collaborative writing platforms play an important role in developing writing skills. In an electronic environment, the student gradually develops their written speech by writing an essay, letter, presentation text, or a short note. Automatic review tools provide immediate feedback to the reader. However, caution is also required when using these tools. Because if a student relies too much on automatic corrections, their ability to think independently and perform grammatical analysis can be weakened. Therefore, the teacher must methodically control the use of such resources.

Another important advantage of e-learning resources is the possibility of individualizing education. Each student has a different level of English language proficiency, learning speed, interest, and needs. In a traditional lesson, it is difficult to fully account for such differences. Electronic resources allow students to select tasks suitable for their level, review the material, practice independently, and track their results. For example, a beginner might do simple lexical exercises, while an advanced learner might work with complex text, debate, or academic

writing assignments. As a result, the educational process acquires a differentiated and personality-oriented character.

At the same time, e-learning resources develop students' independent learning skills. To successfully learn English, only activity during the lesson is not enough. The student must independently listen, read, write, and enrich their vocabulary outside of class. Electronic platforms, mobile applications, and online courses serve as important auxiliary tools in this process. A student can practice English anywhere and at any time. This ensures the continuity of education.

However, there are also certain problems in the process of using electronic educational resources. First, not all teachers possess sufficient digital competence for the effective use of electronic resources. Sometimes the technology is introduced into the lesson only as an external decoration, but it does not serve a clear didactic purpose. For example, showing a video in a lesson alone is not considered an innovation. Video material is effective only when it is linked to students' listening, commenting, or discussion activities. This means that electronic resources must be consciously included in the methodological system.

Secondly, the quality and content of electronic resources is an important issue. There are many materials on learning English on the Internet, but not all of them are methodologically correct, age-appropriate, or scientifically grounded. When selecting a resource, the teacher must evaluate its language level, relevance to the topic, interactivity, reliability, and educational value. Otherwise, incorrectly selected material can lead to confusion, a decrease in interest, or the formation of superficial knowledge.

Thirdly, the excessive use of e-learning resources can also negatively affect the educational process. Learning English is primarily based on live communication, the exchange of ideas, and communicative activity. If the lesson becomes entirely dependent on technical means, the natural pedagogical dialogue between the teacher and the student will weaken. Therefore, electronic resources should be viewed not as a means of completely replacing traditional methods, but as a factor that enriches and increases their effectiveness.

The role of the teacher in improving the methodology of teaching English based on electronic educational resources will also change. Now, the teacher acts not only as a knowledge provider but also as a methodological supervisor who designs the educational process, selects digital resources, manages students' independent activities, and analyzes results. The teacher selects the appropriate resource for the lesson, designs assignments, guides the students' activities, and

provides feedback based on their results. This requires not only knowledge of English but also pedagogical skills, digital literacy, and methodological thinking.

There is also an opportunity to improve the assessment process based on electronic resources. Online tests, automated assessment systems, electronic portfolios, and digital monitoring tools help regularly monitor students' knowledge and skills. This form of assessment allows the student to see the dynamics of their development, identify mistakes, and plan further educational activities. The teacher, in turn, can analyze the strengths and weaknesses of each student and implement an individual approach.

As a result of the discussion, it can be said that e-learning resources have broad opportunities for improving English language teaching methodology. They help organize the educational process in an interactive, individualized, interesting, and productive manner. However, these opportunities will yield the expected results only if they are applied methodologically and carefully planned. The effectiveness of electronic resources depends not on their quantity or technical capabilities, but on their harmony with the lesson goal, student needs, and pedagogical approach.

Theoretical basis

The issue of improving the methodology of teaching English based on e-learning resources is directly related to modern pedagogy, linguodidactics, information and communication technologies, and digital education theories. The theoretical basis of this topic consists primarily of modern approaches aimed at ensuring student activity, independent thinking, communicative activity, and individual development in the educational process.

Electronic educational resources include electronic textbooks, multimedia materials, audio and video resources, interactive exercises, online tests, virtual dictionaries, mobile applications, distance learning platforms, and digital assessment tools that present educational content in digital form and serve to form students' knowledge, skills, and competencies. In English language teaching, such resources are considered not only as an additional visual tool but also as an important didactic factor that improves the content, form, methods, and assessment system of the educational process.

Theoretically, the use of electronic educational resources is inextricably linked to the theory of constructivist education. According to constructivism, knowledge is not provided in a ready-made form, but is actively assimilated by the student and formed on the basis of personal experience. In the process of learning English, a student does not merely memorize a word, grammatical rule,

or text, but acquires new knowledge by applying them in real communicative situations. Electronic resources allow students to conduct independent research, perform interactive tasks, analyze their mistakes, and test their knowledge in practical activities. Therefore, the e-learning environment transforms the student from a passive listener into an active participant.

One of the important theoretical foundations of English language teaching methodology is the communicative approach. According to this approach, the main goal of language learning is not to memorize grammatical rules, but to be able to communicate fluently in the language being studied. Electronic educational resources create broad opportunities for implementing a communicative approach. For example, online conversation platforms, virtual dialogues, video communication tools, interactive tasks, and simulation exercises bring students closer to real-life speech situations. As a result, the English language lesson turns from a process of providing theoretical knowledge into a practical communicative activity.

The competence-based approach also plays an important role in the theoretical foundation of this topic. The competency-based approach implies not only the acquisition of knowledge by the student but also the ability to effectively apply this knowledge in practical situations. This approach to teaching English requires the formation of linguistic, speech, sociolinguistic, discursive, strategic, and intercultural competencies. Using e-learning resources, students develop skills in communicating in various speech situations, analyzing texts, listening comprehension, expressing written opinions, and independently searching for information.

A student-centered approach to teaching English based on e-learning resources is also theoretically important. The level of language proficiency, interests, needs, learning speed, and psychological characteristics of each student vary. Digital resources allow students to select tasks suitable for their level, review materials, practice independently, and work on themselves based on individual results. This serves to differentiate and individualize the educational process.

Theoretically, the effectiveness of e-learning resources is also explained by the theory of multimodal education. Multimodal education involves providing educational information through text, images, audio, video, animation, graphics, and interactive tasks. This approach is especially important in learning English, as language skills are formed not only through written text but also through listening, seeing, pronunciation, and communication. Electronic resources allow

the student to acquire knowledge through several sensory channels simultaneously. This helps to better remember, understand and apply the information in practice.

The activity-based approach to teaching English based on e-learning resources is also of great theoretical importance. The activity-based approach views the student not as a recipient of ready-made knowledge, but as an active subject of educational activity. In English lessons, using electronic resources, students perform activities such as listening, speaking, reading, writing, translation, discussion, project preparation, testing, and self-assessment. As a result, the educational process is directed from theoretical explanation to practical activity.

From the perspective of information and communication technology theory, e-learning resources ensure the openness, flexibility, and continuity of the educational process. While in traditional education, students primarily acquire knowledge during lessons and in the classroom, the educational process through electronic resources is not limited by time and space. The student can learn English independently at home, in the library, or in any other setting. This will put the idea of continuous education into practice.

The use of electronic resources in English language teaching methodology is also based on didactic principles. Firstly, the principle of visualization is more effectively implemented through electronic resources, as the reader more clearly understands the topic through videos, drawings, animations, and graphics. Secondly, the principle of activity is manifested through interactive exercises, tests, and communication tasks. Thirdly, the principle of consistency and sequence is ensured through the phased placement of materials on electronic platforms. Fourthly, the principle of individualization is linked to the possibility of selecting tasks that correspond to the students' level. Fifthly, the principle of the unity of theory and practice is realized through the application of language materials in real communicative situations.

The use of e-learning resources is also theoretically linked to theories of motivation. Motivation is an important factor in learning a foreign language. The gamification, rating system, quick feedback, interactive tasks, and visual materials used in electronic resources increase students' interest. The student sees their achievements, identifies their mistakes, and strives to move to the next stage. This strengthens internal motivation.

Another important issue on a theoretical basis is the digital competence of the teacher. The effective use of e-learning resources requires methodological,

pedagogical, and linguistic preparation from the teacher alongside technical knowledge. When selecting an electronic resource, the teacher must consider its relevance to the topic, age characteristics, language level, interactivity, and the fact that it serves a didactic purpose. Therefore, digital competence becomes an important component of the professional competence of an English teacher.

An analysis of the theoretical foundations of using e-learning resources shows that this process is not only a technological update but also a substantive change in educational methodology. In this process, the learning process is organized at the student's center, knowledge is acquired through practical activity, language competencies are comprehensively developed, and the educational process is enriched with a digital environment.

Thus, the theoretical foundations for improving the methodology of teaching English based on e-learning resources rely on constructivist, communicative, competency-based, personality-oriented, multimodal, and activity-based approaches. These approaches serve to organize English language instruction based on modern requirements, develop students' independent, creative, and communicative activities, and increase educational efficiency.

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